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CHALLENGES OF TEACHING ENGLISH AS A FOREIGN LANGUAGE FOR UZBEK STUDENTS

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Kutlimuratova Barno Xursandbekovna,

teacher at Urgench State University, Urgench, Uzbekistan.

O‘razboyev Abdulla Durdibayevich, professor at Urgench State University,
Urgench, Uzbekistan.

Abstract: This paper examines the challenges of teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL) to Uzbek students. It highlights the lack of English exposure, grammar differences, shortage of qualified teachers, and limited resources as major hurdles. The study discusses best-practice methodologies like CLT, TBLT, CBI, technology-enhanced learning, and learner autonomy. Addressing these challenges requires increased English exposure, improved teacher training, and better resource allocation for effective language learning.

Keywords: TEFL, Uzbek students, challenges, exposure, grammar differences, , Uzbekistan.

English is a global language that is widely used in international communication, business, and education. As a result, the demand for learning English as a foreign language has been increasing rapidly in countries where English is not the primary language. Uzbekistan is one of the countries where the learning of English as a foreign language (EFL) has become more prevalent over the years. However, teaching English as a foreign language to Uzbek students comes with various challenges [1]. In this essay, we will explore the challenges of teaching English as a foreign language (TEFL) to Uzbek students.

As a literature review in the scope of this work, the paper by Hasanova [2] examines the teaching and learning of English in Uzbekistan. The author also explores issues related to foreign-language curriculum innovations, teacher training, and teaching resources. The paper aims to shed light on the challenges and opportunities for English language teaching and learning in Uzbekistan.

Another significant work to note is the paper by Radjabova [3] that examines the hypothesis that involving learners in the selection of course materials and design of the English for Specific Purposes (ESP) course will enhance their interest and motivation, foster their critical thinking skills, and result in effective learning. The literature on learner involvement in course design supports this hypothesis, suggesting that learner autonomy and engagement can lead to improved learning outcomes. Additionally, the literature on ESP highlights the importance of tailoring language instruction to meet the specific needs and interests of learners in order to achieve course objectives.

One of the significant challenges of teaching English as a foreign language to Uzbek students is the lack of exposure to English [4]. Uzbekistan is a country where Uzbek is an official language, with Karakalpak, Tadjik and Russian languages being the other most-spoken languages. Therefore, students do not have sufficient exposure to English in their daily lives, making it challenging for them to learn and understand the language. Most Uzbek students have never been exposed to English until they start learning it in school, which can hinder their motivation and interest in learning the language [5].

Another challenge that Uzbek students face when learning English as a foreign language is the difference between English and Uzbek grammar [6]. To analyze this matter, let us look at the roots of these two languages:

The Uzbek language is a Turkic language (Karluk branch) that is spoken primarily in Uzbekistan, Central Asia, and other nearby regions. It is the official language of Uzbekistan and is also spoken in Afghanistan, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan, Turkmenistan, and Russia [7]. The Uzbek language has been heavily influenced by other languages such as Persian, Arabic, and Russian. It is written in the Latin alphabet since 1992, but prior to that, it was written in the Cyrillic alphabet. The Uzbek language has several dialects, and the standard Uzbek dialect is based on the Tashkent dialect. It has a rich cultural and literary heritage and has produced many renowned poets and writers²⁰.

The English language belongs to the Germanic branch of the Indo-European language family. Within the Germanic branch, English is classified as a West Germanic language, along with German, Dutch, and several other languages. The West Germanic languages are characterized by their use of inflectional suffixes, strong and weak verbs, and complex grammatical structures. Other branches of the Indo-European language family include Romance, Celtic, Slavic, Baltic, and Indo-Iranian, among others²¹.

Considering above mentioned facts, Uzbek grammar is vastly different from English grammar, making it challenging for students to learn and comprehend the English language's grammatical rules. For example, in Uzbek, the word order is subject-object-verb, while in English, it is subject-verb-object. The difference in grammar rules can lead to confusion and difficulties in learning and understanding the language.

Additionally, the lack of qualified English teachers is another challenge that Uzbek students face. Although the Uzbek government has been making efforts to improve the quality of English language teaching, there is still a shortage of

²⁰ More about the Uzbek language: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uzbek_language

²¹ More about the English language: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Uzbek_language

qualified English teachers in the country. Most English language teachers in Uzbekistan are not native speakers of English, and their English proficiency levels may not be high enough to teach English effectively. As a result, students may not receive the necessary instruction to learn English properly.

Moreover, another significant challenge of TEFL to Uzbek students is the lack of resources [8]. Due to economic constraints, schools in Uzbekistan may not have access to adequate resources such as textbooks, audio and video materials, and language laboratories. The lack of resources can make it difficult for students to practice their English language skills, hindering their progress in learning the language.

Here are some of the best-practiced methodologies worldwide to mitigate the challenges of TEFL:

- **Communicative Language Teaching (CLT):** This approach emphasizes interaction and communication between learners and focuses on the development of communicative competence in the target language.
- **Task-Based Language Teaching (TBLT):** This methodology uses real-life tasks as the basis for language instruction, which helps learners to develop the language skills necessary to complete the tasks successfully.
- **Content-Based Instruction (CBI):** This methodology integrates language instruction with content from other subjects, such as science or social studies, to help learners develop both language proficiency and content knowledge.
- **Technology-Enhanced Language Learning:** The use of technology, such as computer-assisted language learning (CALL) software, online resources, and mobile apps, can provide learners with additional opportunities to practice language skills and receive feedback.
- **Learner Autonomy:** Empowering learners to take an active role in their learning process, such as through self-directed learning or peer teaching, can increase motivation and engagement and help learners overcome language barriers.

In conclusion, teaching English as a foreign language to Uzbek students comes with various challenges. The lack of exposure to English, differences in grammar, the shortage of qualified English teachers, and the lack of resources are some of the challenges that Uzbek students face when learning English. To overcome these challenges, it is essential to provide students with more exposure to English, improve the quality of English language teaching, and provide schools with the necessary resources to facilitate effective English language learning. By doing so, Uzbek students can develop their English language skills and have better opportunities in their academic and professional lives. In the end, it is important to note the great efforts being made by the Uzbekistan's government to mitigate above challenges, which will for sure be noticed in the long term.

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ИНГЛИЗ ТИЛИДАН ЎЗЛАШГАН АХБОРОТ ТЕХНОЛОГИЯЛАРИ ТЕРМИНЛАРИНИНГ ЎЗЛАШИШ ОМИЛЛАРИ ҲАМДА УЛАРНИНГ АМАЛДА ҚЎЛЛАШ ҚИЙИНЧИЛИКЛАРИ

МАВЛОНОВА МАВЛУДА ДАВУРОВНА ,
катта ўқитувчи
Муҳаммад ал-Хоразмий номидаги
Тошкент ахборот технологиялари университети,
Тошкент

Аннотация: Ушбу мақолада бугунги кунда барчанинг лисоний луғатида ўзлашишга улгурган АТ терминлари, уларнинг нутқда ишлатилиши, АТ терминларининг инглиз тилидан бошқа хорижий тилларга бевосита ва билвосита ўзлашиш омиллари ҳақида сўз юритилади. Шунингдек инсонлар нутқида ўзлашган сўзларнинг таржима қилишдаги камчиликлар ва қийинчиликлар ҳақида батафсил ёритилган.

Калит сўзлар: АТ терминлар, лисоний тежамкорлик, маъно торайиши ва кенгайиши, терминларнинг ўзлашиш омиллари.

Abstract: In this article we will talk about IT terms that everyone has managed to master in the language dictionary today, about their use in speech, about the factors of direct and indirect mastering of IT terms from English to other foreign